

MULTIFUNCTIONAL FIBRE REINFORCED COMPOSITES: FROM SMART OUT-OF-OVEN MANUFACTURING TO INTEGRATED SENSING AND DE-ICING CAPABILITIES

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The usage of advanced fibre reinforced composites to replace traditional metal components in the field of aerospace, automotive, and renewable energy has been continued increasing due to their high specific stiffness and strength, especially for lightweight structural applications. However, apart from their excellent in-plane mechanical performance, many other properties like electrical and thermal properties still have great potential to improve. The evolvement of nanomaterials during last decade, especially carbon nanomaterials like carbon nanotubes (CNTs) and graphene nanoplatelets (GNPs) has enabled the development of many novel multifunctional composites with good preservation of their mechanical performance with embedded new functionalities like high electrical/thermal conductivity (especially out-of-plane direction), as well as strain sensing and damage sensing for the potential application of online structural health monitoring for structural composite components [1, 2]. Another very important aspect also should be addressed for composite materials is their manufacturing methods, where new technologies with lower energy consumption and more environmental sustainability are always welcome compared to traditional energy intensive autoclave.

In this work, we demonstrate a novel multifunctional composites with embedded strain/damage sensing and de-icing functionalities, which are manufactured via an innovative environmental sustainable and intrinsically safe methods with only 1% energy consumption compared to oven curing. A self-regulating nanocomposite layer consists of GNPs and HDPE with intrinsic positive temperature coefficient (PTC) effect was fabricated [3, 4], and utilised as embedded heating layer for the curing process of thermoset resins. The self-regulating temperature was tuned to the curing temperature of the epoxy resins, so only current was applied to the layer with no external heating sources (Figure 1). Compared with traditional oven heating, the energy consumption was two orders of magnitudes lower, while the temperature profile very similar to oven heating (Figure 2). Due to the consistent temperature control during the curing processes, no obvious difference in mechanical properties can be found between two manufacturing methods.

Figure 1: Illustration of nanocomposite film placed on top of reinforcing fabric during the vacuum assisted resin infusion process.

Figure 2: (a) Temperature comparison between oven and Joule heating process based on nanocomposite film, and (b) energy consumption comparison between two methods, showing clear energy saving with nanocomposite film heating system.

After the composite laminate was cured, the nanocomposite layer is embedded on the surface of the laminate and being utilised as a smart multifunctional layer. Figure 3 shows the in-situ electrical sensing signals for the current multifunctional composites under flexural loading conditions, with clear and consistent sensing signals upon each loading cycle. The de-icing capabilities based on Joule heating has also been examined and presented in Fig. 3, indicating very good heating capabilities based on embedded nanocomposite film.

Figure 3: *In-situ* strain sensing of smart composite under flexural loading, showing great repeatability and consistency of sensing signals; and thermal image of de-icing properties based on Joule heating of smart nanocomposite layer.

In short, this newly developed manufacturing method based on PTC effect of nanocomposite film could provide great energy saving for current oven (out-of-autoclave) manufacturing, and ensure high safety standard due to their intrinsic self-regulating nature. The mechanical and thermomechanical properties like flexural stiffness and glass transition temperature remained at very similar level to previous oven curing methods, confirming the effectiveness of curing process by current safe out-of-oven method. The embedded layer also serve as smart functional layer for various properties like strain/damage sensing and de-icing throughout the components' life, especially for those composite system based on insulating fibres. The current multifunctional composites also provide great flexibility for complex shape manufacturing since HDPE/GNP films can be easily made with desired dimensions. Capital costs also can be saved compared to autoclave or oven curing methods.

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